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CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES

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Annotation. Studying the theory of creating industrial clusters shows that there are several approaches to their organization. It is important to assess whether the American model, the model of South Asian countries, or the model of modern European countries is suitable for the conditions of Uzbekistan. Based on this, the article discusses the specific features of creating textile clusters in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: cluster structures, best practices, innovative activity, integration, management, industrial competitiveness.

Аннотация. Изучение теоретических основ формирования промышленных кластеров показывает, что существуют различные подходы к их организации. Важное значение имеет оценка возможности применения американской модели, модели стран Южной Азии, а также модели современных европейских стран в условиях Узбекистана. В связи с этим в данной статье рассматриваются специфические особенности формирования текстильных кластеров в Республике Узбекистан.

Ключевые слова: кластерные структуры, передовой опыт, инновационная деятельность, интеграция, управление, промышленная конкурентоспособность.

INTRODUCTION

The creation of clusters in the textile industry, which is becoming one of the driving sectors of Uzbekistan's economy, has made it possible to fully process cotton fiber and, at the same time, significantly increase export indicators. While in 2016 the export volume of textile products did not reach even USD 1 billion, by the end of 2023, products worth almost USD 3.5 billion had been delivered to foreign partners [5].

A number of legal and regulatory documents have been adopted to increase the efficiency of the industry, expand its export opportunities and geography, and introduce advanced corporate governance practices. In particular, the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-53 dated January 21, 2022, "On measures to stimulate deep processing and the production of high-value-added finished products at textile and garment enterprises, as well as their export", and No. PF-2 dated January 10, 2023, "On measures to support the activities of cotton and textile clusters, radically reform the textile and garment industry, and further increase the export potential of the sector", serve as the legal basis for supporting the development of the sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

M. Enright, known as one of the founders of the theory of regional clusters, substantiated the formation of competitive advantages at the regional level. In his view, a regional cluster is a geographically concentrated and mutually beneficial association of companies operating in related sectors of the economy [1].

According to E. Chemodanov, another important factor that should be considered in the clustering system of the economy is the active involvement not only of companies from relevant sectors, but also of government institutions and research organizations [2].

The evolutionary development of integration in the cotton and textile industry makes it possible to consider the cluster system in light industry as a promising model of integrated associations and to assess the effectiveness of its formation and development at the regional level. Cluster policy involves the development of the most effective forms of integration. The study of methodological approaches, advanced foreign and

domestic experience in the formation of production clusters shows that a number of conditions are required for the successful implementation of this process:

- the presence of enterprises that use the competitive advantages of the region and are focused on dynamically developing market segments;
- strong chambers of commerce and industry and professional associations;
- an environment of trust and creativity;
- the activity of a large number of small and medium-sized enterprises;
- the presence of research organizations, a high level of entrepreneurial culture, and a qualified workforce;
- well-developed infrastructure supporting industrial development;
- regional government and management policies aimed at supporting and developing clusters;
- continuous interaction among firms within the cluster [3].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article uses observation as one of the primary research methods, the induction method to understand the impact of changes in internal elements on the overall state of the cluster, and the analysis method to divide the process of textile cluster formation into specific parts and stages.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The creation of a system of cotton-textile clusters, as well as agro-industrial clusters, includes several stages (Table 1).

Table 1
Stages of Cluster Formation¹

Stage	Description
Project Preparation	Assessment of the production orientation of participants, coordination of stakeholders' interests, development of a pilot project and a cluster project, formulation of operational principles, and establishment of the regulatory and legal framework for cluster activities.
Analytical Framework	Identification of challenges related to innovative activity within the cluster area, definition of goals and objectives, alignment of the project with available resources and timelines, and continuous monitoring to ensure timely adjustments to the program.
Strategy Development	Determination of the scope of joint activities among participants, development of an innovation-oriented concept for cluster development, preparation of an innovation development program, and formulation of the foundations of the cluster's human resource policy.
Project Implementation	Direct implementation of the cluster project and execution of the planned activities.
Long-Term Development Planning	Monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of cluster relationships, as well as development of scenarios for the long-term sustainable development of the cluster.

Practice shows that the introduction of cluster networks contributes to the optimization of production relationships, enhances the competitiveness of both products and the industry as a whole, and ultimately improves the standard of living of the population in the region. The organization of cluster networks generates numerous benefits at different levels of management, including economic, social, environmental, and other advantages (Table 2).

¹ author's development

Table 2
Advantages of Implementing Cluster Structures²

Management Level	Benefits of Cluster Development
National Economy Management	Implementation of policies that take into account the interests of economic entities; Growth of domestic and foreign investment, contributing to increased competitiveness of both the sector and the national economy; Promotion and adoption of innovative initiatives; Expansion of the export potential of the sector and the national economy as a whole; Achievement of sustainable economic growth.
Regional (Territorial) Management	Strengthening cooperation and integration between business entities and public institutions; Reduction of risks associated with regional economic development; Increase in employment opportunities, contributing to social stability; Enhancement of the region's development prospects, innovativeness, and competitiveness.
Sectoral Management	Expansion of internal interactions within the network; Increased development opportunities through cooperation among enterprises operating in related fields; Introduction of innovative solutions that improve the efficiency of production and other business processes within the sector.
Enterprise Management	Establishment of direct cooperation between manufacturing enterprises and research institutions; Creation of a unified database containing important information on production, sales, logistics, and related activities; Identification of effective solutions to issues arising from interactions among cluster participants; Improvement of profitability and overall performance through the efficient utilization of production and other resources; Contribution to employment growth, poverty reduction, and improvements in the population's standard and quality of life [4].

Thus, the advantages of introducing a cluster system in the agro-industrial complex contribute to improving numerous processes at both the microeconomic and macroeconomic levels of the national economy.

Researchers studying the issues of increasing agricultural efficiency generally classify clustering processes in the agro-industrial complex into three main areas: the production of means of production, agricultural production, and the storage and processing of agricultural products. The effective integration of these areas serves as the foundation for achieving positive outcomes from cluster structures.

It should be noted that the introduction of cluster structures in the industrial sector has contributed to the rapid growth of economic indicators. In particular, an analysis of production performance in the textile industry before and after 2015–2016 shows that the sector experienced significant growth following the implementation of cluster-based development approaches (Table 3).

Table 3
Production Indicators of the Textile Industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Indicators	2010	2015	2020	2025
Industrial output volume, billion UZS	38,119.0	97,598.2	368,740.2	1,101,100.6
Textile products output, billion UZS	4,845.5	13,241.7	36,713.9	134,210.0
Clothing production output, billion UZS	575.8	1,585.3	10,402.4	31,942.1

Source: Compiled by the author based on official statistical data.

The production of textile products increased by 8,396.2 billion UZS between 2010 and 2015, before the establishment of clusters. In the period from 2015 to 2020, after the introduction of clusters in the cotton-textile industry, this increase reached 23,472.2 billion UZS. This indicates that, as the level of clustering in the industry

² author's development

increased, production volumes also grew steadily. In particular, textile production amounted to 36,713.9 billion UZS in 2020, while by 2025 this indicator had reached 134,210.0 billion UZS, representing a growth of more than 3.5 times.

A similar trend can also be observed in clothing production. In 2015, enterprises in the sector produced clothing products worth only 1,585.3 billion UZS. By 2020, this figure had increased more than sixfold, reaching 10,402.4 billion UZS, and by 2025 it had risen further to 31,942.1 billion UZS. These figures indicate the significant contribution of cotton-textile clusters to macroeconomic development and the strengthening of the textile industry's production potential.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above considerations, it can be concluded that the creation of clusters and ensuring their competitiveness largely depend on the effective use of innovative developments. These processes contribute to the modernization of both regional and national economies, improve the efficiency of production and reproduction processes, support the growth of gross regional product, expand the export potential of regions, and enhance overall economic well-being.

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